

Influence of travel motivation aspects on destination loyalty of domestic tourists' visiting Coast region, Kenya

Lawrence Wang'ombe¹, Dr. Joseph Njoroge², Dr. Peace Agufana³

¹Post-graduate Student, School of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Murang'a University of Technology, Kenya

²Senior Lecturer, School of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Murang'a University of Technology, Kenya

³Senior Lecturer, School of Education, Murang'a University of Technology, Kenya

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7147601>

Published Date: 05-October-2022

Abstract: Despite the marginal growth recorded in the tourism sector in Kenya, the domestic visits and estimates fall far below targets and expectations due to a number of reasons affecting tourism demand at this level. The specific objective was to; examine the influence of socio-psychological and destination attributes on destination loyalty among domestic tourists in Kenya with an intention of providing prerequisite information on travel experiences and needs as per the study constructs. Simple random sampling technique was adopted for domestic tourists while data was collected using structured questionnaires. Data analysis carried out using various techniques such as; descriptive and inferential statistical techniques comprising t-test and simple linear regressions were used to examine the significance of the relationships between study variables. In this study, 400 questionnaires were distributed to domestic tourists, while the return rate was 92.7%. From the regression coefficients, results the socio-psychological factors and destination attributes were all significant predictors of destination loyalty at 5% level of significance since the p value was less than 0.0001. The model summary results indicated, R-square = 0.442, implying that socio-psychological and destination attributes factors explains 44.2% of destination loyalty. The null hypothesis was tested and rejected since the results indicated that socio-psychological factors and destination attributes have a significant influence on destination loyalty. It is evident from these findings that the socio-psychological aspects are more predominant when compared with destination attributes. Since, destination attributes and socio-psychological factors explain 44.2% of destination loyalty, 55.8% of the variation is still unexplained, thus the study recommends further study be conducted aimed at establishing other factors influencing destination loyalty.

Keywords: Travel motivation, Destination attributes, Socio-psychological, Destination loyalty, Word of mouth, Revisit intentions, Domestic tourists.

1. INTRODUCTION

Introduction to the Problem

Over the decades, domestic tourism has been noted as the main driving force of travel and tourism sector in major economies globally, accounting for 73% in 2017 and 71.2% in 2018 (TRI, 2021). The tourism sector in Kenya has experienced impressive and sustained growth since 2015 reaching an all-time high of 2.05 million international tourist arrivals in 2019 (GOK, 2020). However, with the outbreak of Covid-19 the scenario has changed greatly implying that Kenya's travel and tourism industry has experienced challenges unknown in the recent history.

As a result of travel restrictions and cancellation of flights which led to a sharp decline of international tourists' arrival at 870,465 in 2021, as compared to 567,848 in 2020, but still low in comparison with 2.05million in 2019 (TRI, 2021). The dismal performance is unpredictable and might continue in the long-run due to several unprecedented issues facing the international tourism market. On the other hand, the domestic tourism has continued to show significant progress for instance between 2015 and 2018, domestic tourism accounted for more than 50% of the total bed occupancy (GOK, 2019). Further, between the period of 2014 to 2018, the number of domestic tourists' bed-nights increased from 2,948,000 to 4,559,000 (TRI, 2021). Further, the domestic tourism market in 2021 recorded 3, 829,900 visitors, 2,567,000 in 2020 and 4,047,300 in 2019 (GOK, 2022). As the country seeks ways for at least stabilizing the industry, there has been consensus that the recovery of Kenya's tourism during and post Covid-19 pandemic period would mainly be supported by the domestic tourism market. The market segment has been key to Kenya's tourism for some time now. With the diverse attractions spread across the country, Kenya now has an opportunity to build on domestic tourism as the next frontier in order to cushion the industry.

Researchers have recognized the heterogeneous aspect of tourists' motivation by proposing visitor typologies based on different constructs such as personality and tourism activity (Kim, 2013; Chiu, 2016). In order to actualize this concept several theories and typologies on travel motivation and destination loyalty were considered in this study.

Equally, most tourism researchers have concentrated their focus on who, when and how tourist make travel decisions but the critical question on why tourists travel remain scantily answered. In attempt to answer this fundamental question, different theories on travel motivation studies were developed over time in an effort to explain travel psychology of tourists. Key among these is the renowned '*Hierarchy of needs*' based on Maslow theory (1971), '*Push and pull factors*' by Dann (1977) and '*Motivators of travel theory*' by Hudman (1989).

Due to the unique nature of tourism, different typologies have been posited implying that these concepts cannot be generalized in terms of its application to all tourists since their travel needs and experiences are diverse. For instance, when a typology is universally applicable to all tourists, it then seems to ignore some fundamental constructs, which weaken the validity of such proposition. This has seen a divide in scholars focusing on domestic travel motives in comparison with the international one (Rather, 2018).

Dann (1977) proposed push and pull motivation theory in tourism research. According to the theory, multiple factors that motivate tourists to visit specific destinations can be categorized into either push or pull motivators. Push factors are at the most basic level, the internal drivers that compel tourists to travel, and are related to; desire to rest, adventure, and transcend isolation, feelings and escape. Push factors are therefore those factors that triggers travel and represent the socio-psychological needs of tourists as spelt out in this study. On the contrary, pull factors mostly associated with the destination amenities such as quality of service, infrastructure and prices. In this study, the researcher operationalizes travel motivations from two aspects namely; socio-psychological factors denoting "push factors" and destination attributes denoting "pull factors".

Importance of the Problem

Although Kenya possesses diverse touristic resources, it hasn't achieved its potential share of the domestic receipts (Kihima, 2015; GOK, 2017). This implies that Kenya as a destination is yet to fully address the strategic potential of the domestic tourism in comparison with the international market. This has led to skewness whereby a lot of marketing and promotional initiatives are geared toward international tourism at the expense of domestic tourism.

As the country seeks ways for at least stabilizing the industry, there has been consensus that the recovery of Kenya's tourism during and post Covid 19 would be supported by the domestic tourism market (TRI, 2021). Industry analysts and experts around the World are of the view that domestic demand would recover faster than international demand (TRI, 2021).

For instance, recent surveys revealed that there is still willingness to travel after the pandemic coupled with much emphasis on low tourist density, sanitary conditions and preferences for destinations with outdoor activities and contact with the nature and away from big cities (Gursoy et al., 2020). With such changing visitor behaviour and uncertainty, the future of the tourism industry is still unknown due to the numerous unprecedented issues affecting the industry hence the need to have a strong domestic tourism market orientation.

Similarly, though the domestic tourists may consume similar tourism products and services just like the international tourists, their travel motives needs and experiences vary considerably. There is need to build the body of knowledge based on factual travel motives, needs and other expectations of domestic tourists. Invariably, it is hard to sustainably develop domestic tourism market in Kenya when it is scantily understood since little has been documented in regard to specific travel motives and behavioural intentions. The aim of this study was to provide essential information on travel experiences and needs of domestic tourists in Kenya as guided by the study constructs.

Research Objective

To examine the influence of socio-psychological and destination attributes on destination loyalty among domestic tourists in the Kenyan coast.

Research Hypothesis

H₀: Socio-psychological and destination attributes have no significant influence on destination loyalty.

2. METHODS

Research design

The study adopted a descriptive research design. According to Siedlecki (2020), a descriptive research design involves an in-depth explanation of a situation. Kothari (2012) noted that a descriptive research design enhances gathering, analysis, summarizing, presentation and interpretation of data for clarification purposes.

Study area

The study was conducted in the most frequented attractions the along Kenyan Coast, comprising North and South Coast; Mombasa, Kilifi and Kwale Counties as per the Economic survey report, (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics – KNBS, 2019). The Coastal region comprises of diverse touristic attractions and is considered major hub for both domestic and international tourists. The key attractions that were sampled included Haller Park, Fort Jesus, Gede Ruins, Jumba la Mtwana, Mnarani Monuments and Marine National Parks and Reserves (Watamu, Mombasa, Diani, Kisite Mpunguti and Mombasa Marine).

The Sample and data collection techniques

The number of domestic tourists visiting the Kenyan coast stands at 42.1% of the total number of visitors at the Kenyan coast recorded, 502,980 translating to 211, 252 (KNBS, 2019).

Thus, Yamane (1967) formula was used to determine domestic tourists sample size as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots \text{Hence, } n = \frac{211,252}{1+211,252(0.05)^2} = 399.24 \approx 400 \text{ domestic tourists}$$

In summary the total number of respondents was 400.

Simple random sampling was adopted for the respondents while structured questionnaires was used to collect data from domestic tourists.

Reliability of the Instruments

To measure the consistency of the scores obtained, and how consistent they are for each individual from one administration of an instrument to another and from one set of items to another, the study used Cronbach’s alpha to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire items (Cronbach, 2011). The Cronbach’s coefficient Alpha of 0.70 was used in this study as the rule of thumb, as shown in table 1

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach’s Alpha	Cronbach’s Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.788	.937	191

Source: (Researcher, 2019)

From the reliability statistics, Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.788 was obtained. This means that the research instruments were reliable as the value of Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Statistics exceeded 0.7 rule of thumb.

Data Analysis

Data was processed prior to any analysis using SPSS version 22. The preliminary data was coded and later analyzed as per the study objectives. Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques such as; t-test and simple linear regressions were used to examine the significance of the relationships among the study variables. Simple regression analysis was adopted in testing the relationship between the study’s variables. The significance of the relevant coefficients of the regression models were fitted.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic analysis

The findings from the study found out that majority of the respondents were male at 60.1% while female respondents were 39.9%. The findings shows that 43.4% of the respondents were aged between 31-40 years, 34.8% were between 18 to 30 years, 16.2% were aged between 41 to 50 years, and 5.7% were aged 50 years and above. Out of the total respondents, 56.9% (211) were married, 36.7% (136) were single while 6.5% (24) were in other categories of marital status (separated/divorced).

41.2% of the respondents had a monthly income of Ksh. 100, 000 and below, 24.3% had a monthly income of Ksh. 200, 001-300, 000, 15.4% had a monthly income of between Ksh. 100, 001-200, 000, 10.5% had a monthly income of between Ksh. 300, 001-400, 000 and 8.6% (32) had a monthly income exceeding Ksh. 400, 000. 60.6% had university education, 31.0% had middle level college education and 7.0% had secondary school education while 1.3% had primary school education.

The Concept of travel motivation

In order to understand the concept of travel motivation the current study operationalized this concept by considering two aspects; socio-psychological factors and destination attributes.

Socio-psychological aspects also referred to as ‘Push factors’ describe the drive for an individual to participate in touristic activities or the internal “igniter” that propels the tourist to travel outside of his/her everyday environment. On the other hand, destination attributes herein referred to as ‘Pull factors’, are the forces that attract tourists to choose a specific tourism products or services and are aroused by destination features, which may include factors like scenic attractions, amenities and historical sites. Push factors influence tourists to travel, whereas pull factors attract them to a given destination once the decision to travel has been made (Baniya, 2016). First, in relation to analysis and discussions, socio-psychological factors was considered followed by destination attributes.

Analysis socio-psychological factors (push factors)

First, in order to understand the socio-psychological factors (push factors) of domestic tourists in Kenya various aspects were considered. The socio-psychological factors, which are intrinsic motivation, describes the drive for an individual to participate in touristic activities or the internal “igniter” that propels tourists’ to travel outside of his/her everyday environment. It denotes the need to escape from everyday surroundings for the purpose of relaxation, social interaction, and discovering new things among others. The socio-psychological factors was operationalized under the following thirteen distinct aspects as depicted in table 2. To test the significance of the Likert scale responses on the socio-psychological factors, t-test was used to test each of the responses from an indifference point of neutrality (that is 3) and the findings are as reported in table 2.

Table 2: t-test Results Based on Socio-psychological factors of domestic tourists

Mean	Test Value = 3				
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
					Lower Upper

Visiting Kenyan Coast gives me great pleasure/excitement	4.1698	26.169	370	.000	1.16981	1.0819	1.2577
The choice to visit Kenyan Coast is fulfilling since I am doing things my own way	4.1617	25.988	370	.000	1.16173	1.0738	1.2496
Kenyan Coast is a destination that I am enjoying away from daily routines	4.0997	23.167	370	.000	1.09973	1.0064	1.1931
Visiting Kenyan Coast makes me experience new and different lifestyle	4.0566	20.695	370	.000	1.05660	.9562	1.1570
Visiting Kenyan Coast makes me feel relaxed body and mentally	4.1698	24.684	370	.000	1.16981	1.0766	1.2630
Kenyan Coast is a place where I always wants to travel for exceptional experience/adventure	3.9946	19.586	370	.000	.99461	.8948	1.0945
Visiting Kenyan Coast enables me have fun	3.9515	19.031	370	.000	.95148	.8532	1.0498
Kenyan Coast gives me platform to interact with friends and relatives	3.8383	14.801	370	.000	.83827	.7269	.9496
Visiting Kenyan Coast enables me meet people with similar interests	3.2695	4.129	370	.000	.26954	.1412	.3979
Kenyan Coast enables me acquire knowledge	4.1429	23.766	370	.000	1.14286	1.0483	1.2374
Visiting Kenyan Coast rekindles good memories and times I have had in the past	3.9946	17.648	370	.000	.99461	.8838	1.1054
Visiting Kenyan Coast enables me re-discover myself	4.0970	21.710	370	.000	1.09704	.9977	1.1964
Kenyan Coast is reasonably priced since it is within my income level	3.5202	8.810	370	.000	.52022	.4041	.6363

Source: Research Data (2020)

The one-sample t-test results reveals significant Likert scale responses on socio-psychological factors were significantly agreed upon at 5% level as shown by p-values that are all less than 0.0001 and mean values approaching 4. On the other hand, the least influential socio-psychological aspects based on mean values was; Visiting Kenyan Coast enables me meet people with similar interests (mean=3.2695, p-value<0.0001).

This implies that socio-psychological factors are significant component of motivation among domestic tourists visiting the Kenyan Coast. The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the Kenyan coast triggers; excitement, enables one to do things their way, pleasurable, relaxes body and mind, enhances socialization, acquire knowledge, rekindles good memories, valuable, create exceptional experiences, among domestic tourists.

These results are in tandem with previous studies, which noted the importance of understanding travellers' value when determining market segmentation (Ali, et al 2015). It emphasizes the importance of understanding the values of both visitors and non-visitors to the attraction for the purpose of expanding patronage and reinforcing the product image of an existing user market segment (Ragb, 2020). For instance, Yousefi and Marzuki (2015) noted that there exist intrinsic factors (push factors) that refer to the desire and mind-frame of the tourist towards a destination. Caber and Albayrak (2016) outlines such factors as what drives an individual want to escape from daily routine, relax, explore new things and socially interact.

The findings demonstrates that the Kenyan Coast is, "fairly priced" as noted by domestic tourists sentiments. This means that for instance if a domestic tourist is purchasing an all-inclusive holiday package it may look exorbitant unlike when someone just walk to a site like Fort Jesus and pay entry charges only.

Interestingly, price does not seem to be the main criterion affecting the selection of the destination, though high cost of holiday including transportation, accommodation, food and beverage affect domestic tourists in Kenya (TRI, 2021). However, in many instances the price of tourism products and services has been singled out as one of the major determinants of tourism demand. The movement of demand curve is influenced extensively by price dynamics, thus affecting tourists flow and consumption patterns in a given destination.

In a previous study, it was noted that most domestic tourists in Kenya were more psychocentric as evidenced by their search for symbols of home like food and drinks rather than being adventuresome (Kivuva, et al., 2014). Thus, the pricing philosophy is purely pegged on the kind of holiday arrangement and orientation being pursued which perhaps explains why most destinations have diverse pricing system.

Analysis destination attributes (pull factors)

Secondly, destination attributes denotes the collection of the various components of a destination, comprising both physical and natural environments, and also services and amenities, which mesmerize tourists. The destination attributes was operationalized under the following seventeen distinct aspects as depicted in table 3. To test the significance of the Likert scale responses on the destination attributes, t-test was used to test each of the responses from an indifference point of neutrality (that is 3) and the findings are as reported in table 3.

Table 3: t-test Results based on Destination Attributes

	Mean	Test Value = 3					
		T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
It is a good place to visit since it is safe and secure	4.13	23.472	370	.000	1.129	1.03	1.22
It is a pleasing destination with buildings and places of historical/archaeological relevance	4.09	21.981	370	.000	1.086	.99	1.18
It is an enjoyable destination with diverse recreational activities	4.20	25.951	370	.000	1.199	1.11	1.29
It is a real holiday adventure with outstanding sceneries and beaches	4.09	21.682	370	.000	1.094	1.00	1.19
It has a good exotic atmosphere to visit	3.81	14.449	370	.000	.811	.70	.92
It has a pleasant weather	3.63	10.587	370	.000	.625	.51	.74
It is easily accessible	3.78	14.118	370	.000	.779	.67	.89
It is easy to access information in regard to the destination	3.89	17.239	370	.000	.892	.79	.99
It has high standards of sanitation & cleanliness	3.17	2.653	370	.008	.170	.04	.30
It is a family-oriented destination	3.88	17.360	370	.000	.884	.78	.98
It offers value for holiday money	3.84	15.457	370	.000	.844	.74	.95
It offers good quality of tourism products	3.91	17.990	370	.000	.911	.81	1.01
It offers good quality of food & beverage	3.89	17.504	370	.000	.889	.79	.99
It offers good quality of accommodation facilities	3.94	18.611	370	.000	.941	.84	1.04
The service providers are reliable & consistent	3.79	15.451	370	.000	.787	.69	.89
Hospitality and friendliness of service providers is top notch	3.87	18.018	370	.000	.868	.77	.96
The service providers makes the effort to understand my needs	3.89	18.150	370	.000	.892	.80	.99

Source: Research Data (2020)

The Likert scale responses as depicted by table 3, were all significantly agreed on apart from (all the p-values in the fifth column are less than 0.0001, with an exception of the aspect 'it has high standards of sanitation and cleanliness' where the overall response was significantly neutral (P-value=0.008 and mean=3.17).

Further, the results indicates that the top five most influential destination attributes based on mean values were; It is an enjoyable destination with diverse recreational activities (4.20), it is a good place to visit since it is safe and secure (4.13), it is a real holiday adventure with outstanding sceneries and beaches (4.09), it offers good quality of accommodation facilities (3.94), and finally, it offers good quality of tourism products and services (3.91).

On the other hand, the least influential destination attributes based on mean values were; It has high standards of sanitation and cleanliness (3.17) which average at 3 (round off) denoting fair agreement. However, though at varying responses were all significant indicators with an average of a mean value of 4; it has a pleasant weather (3.63), it is easily accessible (3.78), service providers are reliable and consistent (3.79), and finally, it has a good exotic atmosphere to visit (3.81). In nutshell, these results imply that all the aspects of destination attributes clues are significance influencers in the travel decision process among domestic tourists' visiting diverse attractions in the Kenyan coast.

Rahmawati (2017) noted that most destinations lack essential information pertaining tourism products and services on offer, which leads to poor product perception and development. Previous studies, noted that many domestic tourists in Kenya lack essential tourist market information. In contrast, the current study noted that, most domestic tourists are fairly equipped with relevant market information (MOTW, 2020). Travel information is particularly crucial during planning and travel decision process since consumer awareness, selection, and choice of tourism, and hospitality products depend heavily on the information available and accessible to tourist (Loureiro, et al., 2020).

Kenya as a nature-based destination and now also endowed with rich ecosystem supporting the emerging exploration of blue economy and diverse water sports activities. Besides such exploration, there is a high likelihood of coastal ecosystem being affected by climate change. There is need for destination managers and policy makers to pursue regional adaptation options in order to reduce destinations vulnerability, increase resilience and take advantage of opportunities presented by climate change within the Kenyan coast (Njoroge, et al., 2020).

The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the Kenyan coast has relatively high standards of sanitation and cleanliness. For instance, Mombasa being the second largest city in Kenya is well developed with relatively high standards of sanitation and cleanliness. Arguably, when choosing the holiday destination, low tourist density and sanitary conditions are the main attributes a destination needs to have especially during and post Covid 19 pandemic (TRI, 2021). This scenario might continue since, tourists show preferences for destinations with outdoor activities and contact with the nature and away from big cities (Giddy et al, 2020; Gursoy et al., 2020).

In addition, Kenyan coast is considered a family-oriented destination for domestic tourists. This concur with the socio-demographic finding which shows that, 56.9% of the respondents were married, exemplifying Kenyan coast as an ideal family-oriented destination. Such findings were supported by recent studies, which noted that 42.1% (KNBS, 2019) of domestic tourists prefer Kenyan coast. All these are key aspects of a progressive and competitive destination. The image of a destination is everything in terms of its popularity and competitiveness (Moon, et al., 2018). Further, most of the serene resort hotels offering accommodation are concentrated in north and south coast (KNBS, 2019). Accommodation being a core tourist product has to be well developed to continue attracting all types of tourist (Nikjoo & Ketabi, 2015).

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the tourism products and services consist of both tangible and intangible aspects, of which the latter is more pronounced. This implies that due to the heterogeneous nature of the tourism industry it is important to note that apart from the vast attraction sites available the quality of services on offer is imperative in triggering travel behaviours of tourists.

Operationalization of destination loyalty concept among domestic tourists in Kenya

The indicators of destination loyalty were operationalized as; intentions to revisit, and intention to recommend (word of mouth).

To test the significance of the Likert scale responses on revisit intentions of domestic tourists, t-test was used to test each of the responses from an indifference point of neutrality (that is 3) and the findings are as depicted in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test Results Based on Revisit Intentions

Revisit intentions	Mean	Test Value = 3					
		t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
I have a high likelihood of revisiting Kenyan Coast within 1-2 years	4.13	24.468	370	.000	1.135	1.04	1.23
I will revisit Kenyan Coast within 1-2 years	4.13	23.745	370	.000	1.127	1.03	1.22
I have plans to revisit Kenyan Coast in the near future	4.24	26.865	370	.000	1.237	1.15	1.33

Source: Research Data (2020)

All the Likert scale responses were significant as shown by one-sample t-test results from an indifference test value of 3 (all the p-values are less than 0.0001 and means approximately 4). The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the revisit intentions as spelt out by statements “I have a high likelihood of revisiting Kenyan Coast within 1-2 years, I will revisit Kenyan Coast within 1-2 years, and I have plans to revisit Kenyan Coast in the near future”, signify that revisit intentions is crucial entity of destination loyalty.

To test the significance of the Likert scale responses on Word of mouth (WOM) of domestic tourists, t-test was used to test each of the responses from an indifference point of neutrality (that is 3) and the findings are as reported in Table 5.

Table 5: t-test Results Based on Intentions to recommend (word of mouth) Perspective

Intentions to recommend (Word of Mouth)	Test Value = 3						
	Mean	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
I will say positive things about visiting Kenyan Coast to other people	4.22	26.571	370	.000	1.221	1.13	1.31
I will recommend visiting Kenyan Coast to others (family or friends)	4.28	29.002	370	.000	1.278	1.19	1.36
I will refer Kenyan Coast to other people who want advice on travel destinations	4.21	25.288	370	.000	1.208	1.11	1.30

Source: Research Data (2020)

As shown in table 5, all the p-values were less than 0.0001 and the means are approximately 4; therefore, it is clear that the Likert scale responses on word of mouth are all significantly agreed on at 5% level of significance. The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the word of mouth as spelt out by statements “I will say positive things about visiting Kenyan Coast to other people, I will recommend visiting Kenyan Coast to others (family or friends), and I will refer Kenyan Coast to other people who want advice on travel destinations”, signify that word of mouth is crucial entity of destination loyalty. Previous studies indicated that word-of-mouth referrals are responsible for 60% of sales to new customers thus becoming a major strategic component for successful destination development (Chi & Qu, 2008). Word of mouth communication also implies that tourists’ are willing to share their experiences with friends and relatives (Khuong, et al., 2017; Hasan, et al., 2019).

Regression Model Summary for the influence of travel motivation aspects on destination loyalty

Regression analysis was conducted to assess the influence of travel motivation aspects on destination loyalty. The model summary results are as shown in table 6.

Table 6: Regression Model Summary for the influence of travel motivation aspects on destination loyalty

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.665 ^a	.442	.439	.50831

a. Predictors: (Constant), destination attributes, socio-psychological factors

Source: Research Data (2020)

The model summary table 6 indicates R-square = 0.442, meaning that destination attributes and socio-psychological factors explain 44.2% of destination loyalty. This means that 44.2% of the variation in destination loyalty can be explained by the model containing destination attributes and socio-psychological factors that is relatively high, so predictions from the regression equation are reliable. It also means that 55.8% of the variation is still unexplained so adding other independent variables could improve the fit of the model.

To examine the influence of travel motivation on destination loyalty the results were analyzed using ANOVA as indicated in table 7.

Table 7: ANOVA Results Showing the influence of travel motivation on destination Loyalty

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	75.187	2	37.594	145.499	.000 ^b
	Residual	95.083	368	.258		
	Total	170.270	370			

a. Dependent Variable: destination loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), destination attributes, socio-psychological factors

Source: Research Data (2020)

The ANOVA table 7 results show that the simple linear regression model between travel motivation aspects and destination loyalty is significant (p-value<0.0001). This indicates that the model is significant in explaining relationship between travel motivation and destination loyalty.

Fan and Hsu (2014), using the push and pull framework, showed that motivation had a strong effect on destination loyalty. Thus, from a theoretical perspective it is worth noting that; experience quality, perceived value, and satisfaction have vital roles in the formation of destination loyalty.

Thus, a destination manager should understand the tenets of tourists' loyalty and ways of meeting and exceeding expectations, which can also be the basis of tailor making or modifying product and services, and at the same time embrace appropriate communication strategies.

In order to examine the significance of the various factors on destination loyalty a regression coefficients model was developed as shown in table 8.

Table 8: Regression Coefficients for Model on the Influence of destination attributes and socio-psychological factors on Destination Loyalty

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.955	.187		5.104	.000
	Destination attributes	.389	.060	.367	6.471	.000
	Socio-psychological	.408	.066	.349	6.156	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Destination Loyalty

Source: Research Data (2020)

From these results destination attributes and socio-psychological factors were regressed against destination loyalty. The regression model shows that all the model coefficients were significant in predicting destination loyalty since all the p-values are less than 0.05. This denotes that destination loyalty is influenced by destination attributes and socio-psychological factors. The regression model is thus fitted as follows:

$$\text{Destination loyalty} = 0.955 + 0.389 \text{ Destination attributes} + 0.408 \text{ Socio-psychological factors}$$

From, table 8, the regression coefficient of travel motivation aspects; destination attributes and socio-psychological factors were 0.389 and 0.408 respectively, with a p-value < 0.0001 which is significant. The null hypothesis was tested;

H_0 : Socio-psychological and destination attributes have no significant influence on destination loyalty.

This means that the regression coefficient of travel motivation is significant (p-value < 0.0001), therefore, the null hypothesis was *rejected* since the results showed significant relationship between these variables and it can be concluded that Socio-psychological and destination attributes have a significant influence on destination loyalty.

It is worth noting, destination loyalty is not limited to tourists' revisits but it can also mean that tourists may act as free advertising agents by referring the destination to their networks of families, friends, relatives, and other prospective visitors (Ragb, 2020). Further, tourist revisits and recommendation intentions may often be affected by a number of variables ranging from perceived attractiveness of the destination to the real destination attributes (Ngoc and Trinh, 2015; Tan, 2017).

Jing and Rashid (2018) analyzed positive and negative consumption emotions and referenced in their study that travellers' emotional reactions are firmly connected with the post-consumption periods of experiences with the destination attribute performance. They demonstrated higher satisfaction level with positive tour experiences that cover climate, culture and history, and destination management. Thus, in order to foster long-term domestic visits to local tourist settings there is need to cultivate stable visits to local natural tourist settings. Therefore, an understanding of how to foster domestic tourists' long-term relationships with these settings is paramount.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results indicated that the most influential destination attributes describing the Kenyan coast were; It is an enjoyable destination with diverse recreational activities, it is a good place to visit since it is safe and secure, it is a real holiday adventure with outstanding sceneries and beaches, it offers good quality of accommodation facilities, and finally, it offers good quality of tourism products. In nutshell, all the aspects of destination attributes clues are significant component of motivation and the subsequent travel decision processes among domestic tourists visiting diverse attractions in the Kenyan coast.

Further, the results indicated that the most influential socio-psychological aspects describing the Kenyan coast were; visiting Kenyan Coast makes me feel relaxed body and mentally, visiting Kenyan Coast gives me great pleasure/excitement, Coast is fulfilling since I am doing things my own way, and finally, Kenyan Coast is a destination that I am enjoying away from daily routines.

Overall, all the socio-psychological factors are significant component of motivation among domestic tourists visiting the Kenyan Coast. The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the revisit intentions is crucial entity of destination loyalty/behavioural intention. The findings though at varying responses clearly demonstrates that the word of mouth is crucial entity of destination loyalty/behavioural intention.

The null hypothesis was *rejected* since the results showed significant relationship between independent and dependent variables, thus it can be concluded that travel motivation has a significant influence on destination loyalty among domestic tourists in Kenya.

5. RECOMMENDATION

From the model summary, table 7 it indicates R-square = 0.442, meaning that destination attributes and socio-psychological factors explain 44.2% of destination loyalty. However, 55.8% of the variation is still unexplained, thus the study recommends further study be conducted aimed at establishing other factors influencing destination loyalty.

Conflict of interest

The researcher wishes to declare no conflict of interests

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher is grateful to various respondents namely; domestic tourists, destination managers and opinion experts for their candid participation during this study. Their devotion and dedicated is well acknowledged, thank you once again.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ali, F., Ryu, K., & Hussain, K. (2015). Creative tourists' experience, memories, satisfaction and behavioural intentions. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, 33(1), 85-100.
- [2] Baniya, R., & Paudel, K. (2016). An analysis of push and pull travel motivations of domestic tourists in Nepal. *Journal of Management and Development Studies*, 27, 16-30.
- [3] Caber, M., & Albayrak, T. (2016). Push or pull? Identifying rock-climbing tourists' motivations. *Tourism Management*, 55, 74-84.
- [4] Chi, C. G. Q., & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism management*, 29(4), 624-636.
- [5] Fan, D. X., & Hsu, C. H. (2014). Potential mainland Chinese cruise travelers' expectations, motivations, and intentions. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 31(4), 522-535.
- [6] Giddy, J. K., & Webb, N. L. (2018). The influence of the environment on adventure tourism: from motivations to experiences. *Current issues in tourism*, 21(18), 2124-2138.
- [7] Government of Kenya (2017). Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. *Economic Survey*. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [8] Government of Kenya (2018). Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. *Economic Survey*. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [9] Government of Kenya (2019). Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. *Economic Survey*. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [10] Government of Kenya (2022). Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. *Economic Survey*. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [11] Government of Kenya (2020). Ministry of tourism and wildlife. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [12] Government of Kenya (2021). Tourism Research Institute. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [13] Government of Kenya (2022). Tourism Research Institute. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [14] Gursoy, D., Chen, J. S., & Chi, C. G. (2020). Theoretical examination of destination loyalty formation. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [15] Hasan, M. K., Abdullah, S. K., Lew, T. Y., & Islam, M. F. (2019). Tourists' satisfaction and destination loyalty: a case study on Cox's Bazar beach of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Leisure and Tourism Marketing*, 6(3-4), 174-193.
- [16] Jing, C. J., & Rashid, B. (2018). Assessing the influence of destination perceived attributes performance on Chinese tourist emotional responses. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Environment Management*, 3(11), 59-70.
- [17] Khuong, M. N., & Nguyen, P. A. (2017). Factors affecting tourist destination satisfaction and return intention—a study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 5(2), 95-102.
- [18] Kihima, B. (2015). Domestic tourism in Kenya: Trends, Initiatives and practices. *Les Cahiers d'Afrique de l'Est/The East African Review*, (50), 22-39.
- [19] Loureiro, S. M. C., Stylos, N., & Miranda, F. J. (2020). Exploring how mindfulness may enhance perceived value of travel experience. *The Service Industries Journal*, 40(11-12), 800-824.
- [20] Moon, H., & Han, H. (2018). Destination attributes influencing Chinese travelers' perceptions of experience quality and intentions for island tourism: A case of Jeju Island. *Tourism management perspectives*, 28, 71-82.

International Journal of Novel Research in Marketing Management and Economics

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (31-42), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [21] Ngoc, K. M., & Trinh, N. T. (2015). Factors affecting tourists' return intention towards Vung Tau city, Vietnam-A mediation analysis of destination satisfaction. *Journal of Advanced Management Science* Vol, 3(4).
- [22] Nikjoo, A. H., & Ketabi, M. (2015). The role of push and pull factors in the way tourists choose their destination. *Anatolia*, 26(4), 588-597.
- [23] Njoroge, J. M., Ratter, B. M., Atieno, L., & Mugabe, I. M. (2020). Employing the enhanced Regional Tourism Sustainable Adaptation Framework with a case study of climate change vulnerability in Mombasa, Kenya. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 20(1), 56-71.
- [24] Nzioka, A. M., Kivuva, A. K., & Kihima, B. O. (2014). Selecting non-classified hotels in Kenya: what really matters for business guests?
- [25] Siedlecki, S. L. (2020). Understanding descriptive research designs and methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), 8-12.
- [26] Tan, W. K. (2017). Repeat visitation: A study from the perspective of leisure constraint, tourist experience, destination images, and experiential familiarity. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 6(3), 233-242.
- [27] Rahmawati, P. I. (2017). *Linking Corporate Social Responsibility, Tourism and Climate Change to Build Tourism Community Adaptive Capacity to Climate Change in Bali* (Doctoral dissertation, Victoria University).
- [28] Yolal, M., Chi, C. G. Q., & Pesämaa, O. (2017). Examine destination loyalty of first-time and repeat visitors at all-inclusive resorts. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [29] Yousefi, M., & Marzuki, A. (2015). An analysis of push and pull motivational factors of international tourists to Penang, Malaysia. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 16(1), 40-56.